

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE UNIVERSE AND MAN IN THE WORKS OF FARIDUDDIN ATTOR

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Annotation: The great philosopher of the East Attar considered the following teachings: existence and the human, formation of the matter, the development of the human. As a real substance the Allah is considered in the ontological theory of Attar, the formation of the all items are based on it. According to the teaching and doctrine of Attar the whole Universe is in the disposal and impact of the Allah. Existence, its rules are also substantiated in the article. Attars ideas regarding the matter, substance and human are compared according to the medieval measures taking into account the views of Greek philosophers. The analysis of the fact that during the course of the timeframe a lot of changes have occurred is revealed through the amalgamation of facts.

Keywords: Existence, Man, matter, substance, ontology

The question of the essence of being studies a special section of philosophy - ontology. In Eastern countries, many scholars have referred to the concept of existence and discussed the place of the universe and man in existence. Abu Nasr Farabi in his work "As-siyasat al-Madina": "Being consists of six stages, which are at the same time the basis of everything that exists, which are connected with each other in the form of cause-and-effect relationships. The first stage is the first cause (as-sabab al-awwal, that is, Allah), the second stage is the heavenly bodies (as-sabab as-sani), the third is the active mind (al-akl al-faol), the fourth is the soul (an -nafs), the fifth is form (as-surat), the sixth is matter (al-modda)," he says.

The views of another well-known scientist of the East, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, on being are set forth in the works "Treatise on Being and the Quality of Being", "Treatise on the Distribution of Beings" and "Donishname". According to Ibn Sina,

existence is unique, and it consists of a necessary foundation, that is, essence, and a possible foundation of existence. Philosopher called the necessary basis "wajib ul-wujud", and the possible basis - "imkan ul-wujud".

In Sufism, the concept of existence is studied as the unity of existence, the unity of knowledge and the unity of existence. The word "Vahdat" means unity and unity. "Existence" means "existence." In the teachings of Wahdat ul-Vujud, existence is considered to be a single whole, which includes inanimate objects, plants, animals, heaven and everything connected with heaven.

The famous theologian Ibn Arabi explains the philosophical theory of wahdat ul-wujud, based on his own style.. He believes that Allah is the home of all creation and the heart of the believing slave is the home of Allah. He does not see anything outside of reality in the world, the scientist sees Him in everything, because He is the receptacle that covers everything.

Abdurrahman Jami analyzed the issue of wahdat ul-wujud as follows: "The universe is one, not more than one. All existence, that which exists in the universe, its external qualities, rays, manifestations, is the manifestation of existence. All existence is one. He is divine."

In Sufism, the real being is Allah. Fariduddin Attar tried to develop this idea. Makhdumi Azam, one of the famous representatives of the teachings of Naqshbandi, systematically and holistically studied everything that exists and divided it into eternal and transient, eternal and mortal, the world of commands and the world of people, the world of being. (being) and the world of Adam (non-being).

Fariduddin Attar comments on the unity of existence in Mantik ut-Tair. These thoughts later find their expression in the views of Ibn Arabi (1165-1240). Analyzing the features of the philosophical innovation of Ibn Arabi about being and the philosophical approach of Fariduddin Attar, one can determine the similarity and difference between the sides of the thinkers' ideas about being.

The following important aspects of the relationship between Allah and the Universe during the time of Fariduddin Attar should be noted:

1. Primordial Existence Is Transcendent to the Universe
2. Primordial existence is absolutely unique
3. Primordial existence is the basis of all things
4. All things are arranged in a strict hierarchical order with respect to their original existence.

The attitude of "Allah-World", presented by Ibn Arabi, was formed on the basis of a completely different principle. Ibn Arabi's ontology emphasizes two entities. According to Ibn Arabi, Allah and the Universe are not opposites, they are in accordance with each other, mutually require each other.. This approach can also be seen in the views of Fariduddin Attar. Some sources even suggest that Fariduddin Attar was a major influence on Ibn Arabi's ideas. In addition, the philosophical views of Fariduddin Attar influenced the work of the famous mystic Mahmud Shabustari. It can be testified that he referred several times to the work of Attar in his work entitled "Secrets of Gulzor".

In his teachings, Ibn Arabi states that the "Third Thing", that is, acts as a link between Allah and the Universe.. It is the "Third Thing" that ensures the unity and integrity of the universe, which consists of two poles of divinity and worldliness. There is no such philosophical structure in the teachings of Fariduddin Attar. Attar did not comment on the "third thing", the mediator between Allah and the universe. At the same time, he does not completely reject such contradictions as "body-soul", "transient world-industrial world". He does not completely reject the ontological division between the Creator (Creation) and the created (creature).

It is generally accepted that the world around us consists of two different realities. They are called objective and subjective reality. The reality that exists outside and independently of our consciousness is called objective reality. That part of reality that is associated with human consciousness and is considered a product of consciousness is called subjective reality. This question is explained in Sufism in terms of consciousness and reason. Objective reality corresponds to the concept of

material existence, and subjective reality corresponds to the ideal, spiritual form of existence.

Fariduddin Attar is portrayed as a scientist who thoroughly studied natural phenomena.

He said to the sea: O Benihayat!

Your silence is terrible

If Veil moves, wave, nail st,

sink the entire ship.

The sea may seem calm, but in fact the reverse process is happening in it. He insists that the secret lies behind the silence, that if it is acted upon by the wave as an impulse, its true form will be revealed.

Fariduddin Attar emphasizes the problem of social existence. The hierarchical structure of society emphasizes that a person can achieve his position in society through his work. He bases his stories on the concept of a "just king" and links all his dreams to that king. Recognizes the problem of social justice.

In a word, in the works of Fariduddin Attar, a prominent representative of Eastern mystical philosophy, the problem of ontology is revealed in a religious context. The mystic tried to analyze the phenomena of nature, forms of existence, the relationship between the Universe and man, and made unique conclusions. In our opinion, Fariduddin Attar was one of those scholars who loved wisdom.

Literature

1. Зоиров, Э. Х. (2021). Вопросы онтологии природы в учении махдumi азам. ACADEMICIA: Международный междисциплинарный исследовательский журнал , 11 (5), 91-94.

2. Зоиров, Э. Х. История, археология, религиоведение. Актуальные исследования, 48.

3. Наврўзова, Г. (2005). Нақшбандия тасаввуфий таълимоти ва баркамол инсон тарбияси. Тошкент:“Фан, 233.

4. Наврўзова, Г. Н. (2021). Махдуми Аъзам Нақшбандия асоси бўлган тўрт калима хусусида. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(3), 188-199.
5. Nematovna, N. G. (2021, February). The essence of Abu Ali Sina's treatise on birds and the influence of mystical ideas on its development. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 19-23).
6. Aminovna, B. G. (2021). The role of social system and political ideas in achieving human prosperity. *Thematics Journal of Education*, 6(November).
7. Sultanova, L. (2021). The historical roots of spiritual education of youth. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 461-463.
8. Каримов, Б. (2011). Гармонизация взаимоотношений государства, общества и человека как основа справедливого общества. постановка вопроса. *Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество*, 8(1), 71-73.
9. Karimov, B. K. (2021). Harmony Of Mind And Spirit. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(05), 230-234.
10. Темиров, Ш. Т., & Азимов, А. А. (2016). Экономический и культурный рост народов центральной азии в IX-X веках. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 104-105).
11. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). Политическая и социальная жизнь в бухарском эмирате во взглядах ахмада дониша. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 66-67).
12. Нурматова, Н. У. (2017). Применение мультимедийных технологий в образовательных учреждениях. *Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука*, (6), 25-27.
13. Мухамеджанова, Л. П., & Вахидова, М. Т. (2015). Применение новой педагогической технологии в общественных дисциплинах в процессе подготовки педагогических кадров ССиПО. *Молодой ученый*, (22), 840-842.

14. Рахмонова, М. (2021). Патриотические идеи в творчестве Фитрата: теоретическая и практическая гармония. *Academicia: международный многопрофильный исследовательский журнал* , 11 (2), 1466-1474.
15. Санжар, М. (2020). Взгляды Фаридуддина Аттара на бытие. *Международный журнал прикладных исследований. ИДЖАР* , 6 (6), 34-36.
16. Муродов, С. А. (2009). Ибн Сино, Аттор ва Навоий асарларида кушлар тимсоли. *Имом ал-Бухорий сабоқлари», Маънавий-маърифий, илмий-адабий журнал. Тошкент* , 273-276.
17. Санджар, М. Одним из факторов чистоты сердца является Футуват. *Международный журнал инноваций в инженерных исследованиях и технологиях* , 98-101.
18. Мурадов, С. А. Современные методы философии и их значение в развитии мышления человека. *Актуальные исследования*, 51.
19. Bafoev F. AFGHANISTAN DURING THE PANDEMIC ERA: DIFFICULTIES, ACHIEVEMENTS, PROSPECTS //Central Asia & the Caucasus (14046091). – 2020. – №. 4.
20. Bafoev F. LIBERAL ISLAM IN THE CONTEMPORARY WORLD: NEW LANDMARKS OF TRUMP'S ADMINISTRATION //Central Asia & the Caucasus (14046091). – 2019. – Т. 20. – №. 2.
21. Feruz B. Mid-term stimuli, basic principles, and readjustments: America in Central Asia //Central Asia and the Caucasus. – 2015. – Т. 16. – №. 2. – С. 26-35.
22. Bafoev F. М. О НЕКОТОРЫХ КОНТУРАХ НОВОГО МИРОВОГО ПОРЯДКА: ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ, ПРОГНОЗЫ, ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 12. – С. 388-390.
23. Murtazoevich B. F. Sustainable development goals and synergies of world politics //European science review. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 1-2. – С. 59-61.

24. Bafoev F. M. About some circuits of a new world order: evolution, forecasts, prospects //ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – T. 12. – №. 92. – C. 388-390.
25. Sobirovich T. B. A study of national and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 5. – C. 417-421.
26. Sobirovich T. B. Interethnic Harmony And Religious Tolerance-An Integral Part of The Ancient Traditions Of The Uzbeks.
27. Turdiev B. S. EVOLUTION OF IDEAS AND VIEWS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEMOCRATIC SOCIETY AND SPIRITUAL RENEWALS //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2020. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 209-217.
28. Sobirovich T. B., Ikrom o'g'li I. M. ISSUE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY IN THE VIEWS OF EASTERN THINKERS //" ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2022. – C. 111-114.
29. Sobirovich T. B. National and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 1. – C. 334-338.